

Contribute to Good Data for the NNLM

The Network of the National Library of Medicine (NNLM) seeks to advance the progress of medicine and improve public health by providing equal access to biomedical information and improving the public's access to information for informed, health-related decision-making.

Data and data quality are fundamental to achieving the NNLM's mission.

Each NNLM staff member has a role to play with specific responsibilities, and everyone is accountable for data quality and completeness. Use this guide to determine your **data role** and how you can contribute to data quality and completeness to further advance the NNLM's mission.

NNLM Data Roles	
Data Champion	An individual who is responsible for data, uses data, or cares about meaningful data-driven insights and impact
Data Steward	Units that are responsible for data infrastructure and standard operations; data caretakers (e.g., OET, NWSO, NEC)
Data Provider	Organizations, units, and their team members who are asked for data to satisfy regular reporting requirements or special "data cells" (e.g., NNLM RMLs, offices, centers)
Data Requestor	Units that request data for evaluation or reporting purposes or on behalf of other key partners (e.g., OET, NEC)

Best Practices for Good Data

NNLM

Best Practices for Data Champions

Best Practices for Data Stewards (NWSO, NEC, OET)

Best Practices for Data Providers

Best Practices for Data Requestors (NEC/OET)

